

COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING ITS COMPETENCE AND PRICIPLES

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Abstract

Along with Communicative language teaching, all the types of methods have their principles, competences, features which form them. CLT have 4 competences and 6 principles which are described in the article given below.

Key words: *Grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, strategic competence, principles of CLT.*

In ELT all of the methods possess distinctive features (principles and competences) which make them differ from each other and provide different ways to teach the learners. It is formed by scholars that communicative competence possesses its several principles and competences, so in this article below we will provide information on this features of CLT and scholars views.

As it mentioned before, Dell Hymes introduced “communicative competence” on the basis of Chomsky’s notions competence and performance, He believed that second language acquisition, to acquire a language, learners should go beyond the language rules, but also how to communicate using those rules, he stated that “communicative competence is the aspect of our competence that enables us to convey and interpret messages and negotiate meanings interpersonally within specific contexts” (Brown,2007:219)

Hymes stated that the speaker needs to communicate the language and to be able to use it according to the sociocultural environment. This means that the speaker of foreign language should use the language in a specific context. This idea interpreted by Bachman into communicative language ability. (Bachman 1990; in Hedge 2000: 44_46) .Canale and Swain (1980) and Savignon (2000) conceived communicative competence in terms of fourcomponents: grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociocultural competence, and strategic competence. (Savignon, 2001 in Celce-Murcia, 2001: 17).

4.1. Grammatical Competence: Brown states that the grammatical competence “encompasses knowledge of lexical items and rules of morphology, syntax, sentence grammar, semantics and phonology” (Brown, 2007; in Canale and Swain, 1980: 29). In other words; the ability of students’ to produce accurately structured comprehensible utterances.

4.2. Sociolinguistic Competence: it helps the speakers to be “contextually appropriately” (Hedge, 2000:50). This means to use socio cultural messages in meaningful ways.

4.3. Discourse Competence: According to Brown (2007:220) discourses competence “the ability to connect sentences ...and to form meaningful whole out of a series utterances” In other words; the speaker’s ability to shape and communicate purposely using cohesion and coherence.

4.4. Strategic Competence: for Canale and Swain strategic competence it is “how to cope in an authentic communicative situation and how to keep the communicative channel open” (Canale and Swain, 1980; in Hedge 2000:53) in other words, the learners’ ability to enhance the effectiveness of communication.

Principles of Communicative Language Teaching The main characteristics of communicative language teaching are identified by Brown (2000: 46) as:

1. Classroom goals are focused on all of the components (grammatical, discourse, functional, sociolinguistic, and strategy) .of communicative competence; In other words; students should not only learn the grammatical rules and memorize vocabulary but also know how to use them in a given situation.

2. Language techniques are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes, organizational language forms are not the central focus but rather aspects of language that enable the learner meaningfully engaged in language use. In other words; the different activities or tasks which are used in the classrooms to help students to use the language for meaningful purposes.

3. Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques. At times fluency may have to take on more important than accuracy in order to keep learners meaningfully engaged in language use. In other words; teachers focus more on fluency since the primary goal of CLT is getting students to communicate meaningfully

4. Students in a communicative class ultimately have to use the language productively and receptively in unrehearsed contexts outside the classroom; classroom tasks must therefore equip students with the skill necessary for communication those contexts. In other words students must be provided with the important skills needed to

communicate in real world context

5. Students are given opportunities to focus on their own learning process through an understanding of their own styles of learning and through the development of appropriate strategies for autonomous learning.

6. The role of the teacher is that of a facilitator and a guide.

These characteristics show the main focus of communicative language teaching. To sum up; CLT enables students to communicate in the foreign language using the different types of communicative competence. However; the language techniques encourage them to use the target language in different situations. In addition; communicative language teaching pays less attention to accuracy the degree to which learners use target language is remarkably free of errors, students errors are tolerated into some extent since it focuses more on meaning and fluency which helps students to communicate spontaneously, finally the teacher in CLT approach is a facilitator not a controller.